
Effectiveness of Sales Related Marketing Polices in SKG Sangha, Khed, Satara

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Abstract:

Aiming of this article to understand existing sales related marketing polices of the organization (SKG Sangha) and critically analyze existing sales related marketing polices by using a close ended structured schedule, discussion and observation. SKG Sangha dedicated to promoting sustainable development, particularly in rural areas, through the implementation of biogas plants and other renewable energy solution, there were Seventy-two farmers and three sales executives are considered for collecting feedback. The result shows that SKG Sangha product policies mainly focused on availability of tailored bio gas system, less maintenance of the product and innovate and efficient technology of product policy. The promotion policies mainly focused on review from testimonials to influence their decision at the specific villages. Farmers inclined towards the idea of tailored biogas system because they can reduce energy costs and provide a sustainable of power. Regarding affordable pricing, government support and easy access to technical assistance make them to adopt biogas system. In distribution policy in specific regions can be helpful to reach the product in areas where it's most needed. However, they feel the policy should consider local need, available resources, and ease of access. Farmers think that using testimonials and reviews from other farmers can be a great way to promote biogas systems. Farmers believe that real-life stories and demonstrations are more convincing than just advertisements. However, they would like to see honest feedback, including both advantages and challenges, to make informed decisions. SKG Sangha's sales related marketing policies are enough efficient. However, there are key areas for improvement to further enhance sales effectiveness and market reach.

Keywords: Sales Related Marketing Policies, Biogas system, SKG Sangha, Sustainable development, farmer

Introduction:

SKG Sangha, a non-governmental organization based in India, has been at the forefront of promoting sustainable energy solutions, particularly biogas plants. Biogas plants convert organic waste materials, such as animal manure and kitchen waste, into biogas, a clean and renewable source of energy. This technology not only provides an eco-friendly alternative to traditional fuels but also helps manage waste effectively and produces nutrient-rich

fertilizer as a byproduct.

SKG Sangha is an organization dedicated to promoting sustainable development, particularly in rural areas, through the implementation of biogas plants and other renewable energy solutions. As a pioneer in this sector, SKG Sangha has established itself as a key player in providing environmentally friendly energy alternatives to communities, especially in regions where traditional energy access is limited. The

organization's mission aligns with the global push towards sustainable energy, making its sales-related marketing activities crucial for both business growth and environmental impact.

A sales policy is a set of guidelines and rules that govern how a company conduct its sales activities. Sales policy outlines the processes, procedure, and expectation that sales teams, should follow to ensure consistency and efficiency in their sales efforts. Sales executive's roles is not only to determine, but to administer, policies laid down by higher management. At the other extreme, the sales executive bears sole responsibility for determining sales -related marketing policies- subject, of course, to top management approval. Sales related marketing policies directly influence the jobs of sales executives. SKG Sangha's biogas plant is struggling to increase sales. Sales executives failed to reach their desired target. Organization finding difficult to organize their sales effort and also to control their sales team. Therefore, there is need to set the sales related marketing polices to sale these biogas plant.

Review of Literature:

(Mohammed Khaleel Jameel, January 2024) This articles highlights process of biogas and how it is obtained and what is chemical mixtures of gases generated by biodegradable material without presence of oxygen. Also discussed about advantages and disadvantages of biogas.

(Marta Lisiak-Zielinska, 2023) This article examines public awareness of biogas plants and analyses the perception of public on biogas plants as a renewable energy. The findings reveal that biggest disadvantages of biogas plant are odors but generate production energy and heat. Respondents negatively perceived landscapes with biogas plants. But the visual assessment for operating biogas plant indicated no negative impact on the landscape.

(Monika & Chandan, 2020) This articles evaluated marketing strategies of Compressed biogas companies and not worked on sales related policies

(Kougias & Angelidaki, 2018) This review summaries current state and presents future perspective related to anaerobic digestion process for biogas production. Author thinks that biogas sector is rapidly growing and novel achievements create the foundation for constituting biogas plants as advanced bioenergy factories.

After analyzing the previous research papers, it is find out that most of research paper are based awareness of biogas plants, production, opportunities, perception of public, production process, potential, present scenario, review papers etc. This gap motivates to the researcher to conduct the study on sales related marketing efforts of the biogas plant organization and to know more about the opinion of farmers towards this item as it mainly based on Agriculture.

Methodology:

Present article proposed to Understand Existing Sales Related Marketing Polices of the Organization and to Critically Analyze those policies. Collected data has been analyzed with the help of statistical tools like Frequency, percentage, Mean and standard deviation. The present study is descriptive and analytical in nature. A close ended structured Schedule, Discussion and Observation are the sources used to collect the primary data. Secondary data is collected with the help of Internet, Company website, etc. Sample unit is Farmer and sales executives. Of these Interview conducted to know the opinion and information about the existing sales related marketing policies. The population of sales executives is Three and farmers are finite. Seventy-two farmers and three sales executives are considered for study. Census sampling preferred for sales executives and

convenient sampling method to select farmers.

Data Analysis and Presentation:

Sales Related Marketing Policies of the organization can be described as Product policies, pricing policies, distribution policies and promotion policies.

SKG Sangha **product policies** focused on Warranty period, discounts for bulk purchases, return policy, after sales service, maintenance service, variety, durability and reliability of the product, innovative and efficient technology of bio gas plant. Less maintenance, tailored product, customized solution, high quality standard, long term performance, ensure reliability and training and workshop sessions organized to educate users. In **pricing policy** SKG Sangha claims that they are giving competitive pricing to bio gas plant, giving flexible and suitable financial option, sufficient discounts, assistance for subsidies and grants, delivers quality and value to the customer, transparency in pricing and hidden charges, affordable to the customer and it is cost saving plant. SKG **sangha's distribution policy** claims their installation services are professional and

efficient, ease availability and accessibility to the organization, overall distribution services, strictly observed the schedule, installation process is smooth and efficient, installation and guidance by qualified technician or installer, direct distribution option is available, demonstration site is available. In **promotion** SKG sangha provides sales promotion incentives, their promotional information is clear, they do early awareness, group incentives, attractive promotional activities, organizing awareness campaign to educated the farmers, prefer social platforms for promotional activities, provides education materials, do motivation through success stores and take review from testimonials to influence by local leaders and environmental issues.

Researcher conducted survey to examine the results of sales related marketing policies of the SKG sangha in 10 villages in Satara taluka viz. KasaiMala, Ambawade, Karanje, Kusavade, Limb, Mhasave, Shelkewadi, Shendre, Varye and Valse to collect the feedback. Analyzed data presented in tabulation with respective interpretation to reach to the findings and conclusion.

Table No. 1 : Farmers 'Opinion on Product Policy

Sr.	Statement	Kasai Mala				Ambawade				Karanje				Kusavade				Limb			
		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfaction		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
1	Warranty period offered by the Organization	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0.5	5	0	5	0	4.75	0.6	5	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.9	0.3
2	Discounts for bulk purchases offered by organization	4.17	0.4	4.25	0.5	4.2	0	4.4	0.4	4.67	0	4.67	0	4.25	0.5	4.25	0	4.1	0.6	4.4	0.3
3	Return policy for bought products	4.5	0.7	4.5	0.8	5	0.5	4.8	0.6	5	0.6	4.67	0.6	4.25	0.5	4.25	0.5	4.6	0.3	4.6	0.5
4	The performance of the biogas plant after installation	4.83	0.4	4.92	0.3	4.6	0	4.6	0.5	4.67	0	4	0.6	4.75	1	5	1	4.8	1	4.6	0.7
5	Availability of maintenance Services	4.58	0.7	4.5	0.9	4.4	0.6	4.6	0.6	4.33	0.6	5	0.5	5	0.5	4.75	0	4.5	0.4	4.8	0.5
6	Product Variety with animal waste and kitchen waste	4.75	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.8	0.6	5	0.6	5	0.6	4.67	0	4.25	0.5	5	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.7	0.4
7	Product durability and reliability	4.83	0.4	4.92	0.3	4.6	0.5	4.8	0	5	0	5	0.6	5	0	4.5	0	4.9	0.5	4.9	0.5
8	The biogas plant's innovative and efficient technology.	4.83	0.4	4.25	0.5	4.8	0.6	5	0.5	4.33	0	3.67	0	3	0.5	4.75	0.6	4.6	0.3	4.7	0.3
9	Less maintenance of the product	3	0.7	3.17	0.3	4.2	0.5	2.6	0	4.33	0.6	4.67	0.5	4	0	3.75	0.5	3.9	0.5	3.5	0.5
10	Availability of Tailored bio-gas system	3.92	0.9	4.5	0.7	4.2	0.5	4.4	0.9	4.33	0.6	4	0.6	4.5	0.5	4	0.5	3.5	0.9	4.2	0.9
11	Availability of customized Solution	4.5	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.2	0.5	4	0.9	4.67	0.8	4.33	0	4.5	0.8	5	0.5	4.4	0.8	4.9	0.6
12	High quality standard product	4.75	0.5	4.83	0.4	4.6	0.8	4.4	0.3	4.33	0.6	5	0.2	4.75	0.6	4.5	0	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.3
13	Long term performance of the Product	4.58	0.7	4.83	0.4	4.6	0.6	4.8	0.6	4.67	0.5	4.33	0	5	0.5	4.75	0.6	4.5	0.5	4.8	0.4
14	Product Ensure reliability	4.33	0.7	4.42	0.7	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.5	5	0.6	5	0.6	4.25	0	4.5	0.5	4.7	0.9	4.8	0.4
15	Training and workshop sessions organized to educate users	4.92	0.3	5	0	4.8	0.5	4.8	0.5	5	0	5	0	4.75	1	4	0.6	4.5	0.5	4.7	0.4

Mhasave				Shelkewadi				Shendre				Varye				Valse			
Satisfaction Level		Importance Level																	
Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.																
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.7	5	0.5	5	0.5	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	4.5	0.7	5	0
4.13	0.4	4.25	0.4	4.2	0	4.2	0	4	0	4.11	0.3	4.3	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.5	0.7	5	0
4.75	0.4	4.88	0.5	4.8	0.5	5	0.5	4.56	0.7	4.56	0.7	4.7	0.5	4.7	0.5	4	0	5	0
4.63	0.5	4.75	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.6	0	4.67	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.5	0.7	5	0
4.38	0.5	4.25	0.5	4.6	0.6	4.8	0.6	5	0	5	0	4.5	0.5	4.8	0.4	4.5	0.7	5	0
4.75	0.7	4.88	0.5	5	0.6	5	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.78	0.4	4.8	0.4	4.8	0.4	4	0.4	5	0
5	0.5	5	0.4	4.75	0	4.4	0	4.78	0.4	4.78	0.4	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.4	4.5	0.7	4	0.5
4.63	0	4.38	0	4.6	0.5	5	0.6	4.89	0.3	5	0	4.5	0.5	4.5	0.5	4	0.4	4.65	0.6
3.88	0.5	3.88	0.7	4	0.6	3.6	0	3.67	0.5	3.78	0.6	3.3	0.6	4.9	0.3	3	0	4.15	0.1
4.38	1	4.75	1	4.8	0.7	4.8	0.9	4	0.9	4.44	0.7	4.5	0.7	4.2	0.3	5	0	5	0
4.63	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.2	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.44	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.4	0.7	4.2	0.9	4	0	4.12	0.2
4.5	0.5	4.63	0.5	4.6	0.8	4.8	0.6	4.56	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.6	1	4.8	0.4	4	0.4	4.5	0.6
4.5	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.6	0.6	4.6	0.5	4.89	0.3	4.89	0.3	4.7	0.5	4.6	0.5	4	0.4	4	0
4.5	0.5	4.63	0.5	4.6	0.6	4.8	0.6	4.56	0.5	4.56	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.6	1	4.5	0.7	4.5	0.3
4.63	0.8	4.63	0.7	4.6	0.6	5	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.89	0.3	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.4	5	0	5	0

Table No.1 depicts that SKG sangha is successful in delivering bio gas plant in most of the villages as per their designed policy as there is no difference between mean score of importance level and satisfaction level. However, there is slight difference in the opinion of farmers in Kasai Mala, Limb regarding availability of tailored

bio gas system. Ambawade, Varye and Valse farmers' having less importance regarding less maintenance of the product but are highly satisfied with this statement. Kusawade farmers' importance level is high regarding the biogas plant's innovative and efficient technology but satisfaction level is neutral.

Table No. 2: Farmers 'Opinion on Pricing Policy

Sr.	Statement	Kasai Mala				Ambawade				Karanje				Kusavade				Limb			
		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.																
1	Competitive pricing of biogas plant	4.5	0.7	4.92	0.3	4.8	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.33	0	5	0	5	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.4	0.5	4.4	0.5
2	Flexible and suitable financial options.	4.17	0.4	4.33	0.5	4.2	0.5	4.4	0.5	4.67	0.5	5	0	4.25	0	4.5	0.5	4.4	0.7	4.3	0.7
3	Sufficient discounts and promotional	4.83	0.4	4.67	0.5	5	0.5	5	0.6	4.67	0.6	5	0	5	0.5	4.75	0.6	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.5
4	Organization offer subsidies and grants with the assistance of Govt	4.83	0.4	4.92	0.3	4.8	0	5	0	5	0.6	4.67	0	5	0	5	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.7	0.4
5	Price delivers quality and value.	4.5	0.7	4.5	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.8	0	4.33	0	4.67	0.6	4	0	5	0	4.9	0.4	4.9	0.5
6	Transference in pricing communication and absent of hidden charges.	4.42	0.9	4.5	0.9	4.4	0.5	4	0.5	5	0.5	4.33	0.6	5	0	4.5	0	4.7	0.3	4.5	0.3
7	Affordability of the product	4.58	0.5	4.75	0.4	5	0	4.8	0.3	4.33	0.5	4.33	0.6	4.75	0	5	0.6	4.5	0.5	4.7	0.5
8	Long term energy and cost saving plant	4.67	0.5	4.75	0.4	4.8	0	5	0.5	5	0.5	4.67	0.6	4.5	0.5	4.5	0	4.8	0.7	4.8	0.7

Mhasave				Shelkewadi				Shendre				Varye				Valse			
Satisfactio		Importanc																	
Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.																
5	0.5	5	0.7	5	0.9	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0
4.13	0	4.13	0	4	0	4.2	0	4.44	0.5	4.56	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.6	0.5	5	0	5	0
5	0.4	5	0.4	5	0	5	0.5	4.44	0.5	4.56	0.5	4.9	0.3	4.8	0.4	5	0	5	0
5	0	5	0	4.8	0	5	0	5	0	4.89	0.3	5	0	4.9	0.3	5	0	5	0
4.5	0	4.5	0	4.8	0.5	4.6	0	4.78	0.4	4.89	0.3	4.8	0.4	4.9	0.3	4.6	0.5	5	0
4.5	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.6	0.9	4.67	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.5	0.7	4	0.1	5	0
4.63	0.7	4.75	0.7	4.6	0.6	5	0.6	4.78	0.4	4.89	0.3	4.9	0.3	4.9	0.3	4.52	0.5	4	0
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.5	4.8	0.6	4.8	0	5	0	5	0	4.9	0.3	4.9	0.3	4.6	0.8	5	0

Table No.2 reveals that SKG sangha importance level and satisfaction level of is quiet successful in pricing policy as there farmers in 10 villages. is no noticeable difference between the

Table No. 3: Farmers’ Opinion on Distribution Policy

Sr.	Statement	Kasai Mala				Ambawade				Karanje				Kusavade				Limb			
		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfaction		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
1	Installation service are professional and efficient.	4.75	0.4	5	0	5	0.5	4.8	0	4.67	0	5	0.6	5	0.6	5	0.6	4.9	0.4	4.9	0.4
2	Ease Availability of product and accessibility of the organisation	4.5	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.4	0	4.4	0.5	4.33	0.6	5	0	4	0	4.5	0	4.2	0.3	4.4	0.3
3	Overall distribution Services	4.58	0.6	4.67	0.6	4.8	0.6	5	0.6	4.67	0.6	5	0	5	0	5.75	0.6	4.7	0.4	4.7	0.5
4	Strictly observed the delivery schedule	4.5	0.5	4.58	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.8	0	4.67	0.6	4.67	0	4.5	0	5	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.5	0.5
5	The installation process smooth and efficient.	4.67	0.5	4.75	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.67	0.6	5	0.6	4.5	0.6	4.5	0	4.5	0.5	4.7	0.5
6	Installation and guidance by a qualified technicianor installer	4.67	0.5	4.67	0.6	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.5	4.33	0.6	4.33	0	4.5	0.6	4.25	0.6	4.6	0.7	4.5	0.5
7	Direct Distribution option	4.58	0.9	4.67	0.5	5	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.67	0.6	4.67	0.2	4.5	0.6	4.75	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.7	0.5
8	Collaborative assistance have wide coverage	4.42	0.9	4.08	0.3	4.6	0	4.2	0.5	5	0.6	4.33	0.6	4	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.7	0.4	4.78	0.5
9	Focus on specific region	2.83	1	3.42	0.3	2.63	0.6	3.2	0.3	4.33	0.6	4.67	0.6	2.5	0.4	3.5	0.6	2.9	0.5	3.12	0.7
10	Establishment of demonstration sites	4.75	0.6	4.5	1	3.4	0.3	4.8	0.6	5	0	4.67	0.6	5	0	4	0.7	4.6	1	4.1	0.5

Mhasave				Shelkewadi				Shendre				Varye				Valse			
Satisfactio		Importanc																	
Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.																
4.88	0.4	4.88	0.4	4.8	0.5	5	0.5	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0
4.25	0.4	4.29	0.4	4.2	0.5	4.2	0	4.33	0.5	4.44	0.5	4.4	0.5	4.5	0.5	5	0	5	0
4.75	0.5	4.5	0.5	4.8	0.5	5	0.5	4.89	0.3	4.89	0.3	4.8	0.4	4.8	0.4	5	0	5	0
4.63	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.4	0.5	4.8	0	4.89	0.3	4.89	0.3	4.9	0.3	4.9	0.3	5	0	5	0
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.5	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.5	4.56	0.5	4.89	0.3	4.9	0.3	5	0	4.5	0.3	5	0
5	0.4	4.88	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.4	2.52	0.1	4	0
4.75	0	4.75	0.4	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.5	4.89	0.3	4.78	0.4	4.9	0.3	4.8	0.4	4.68	0.6	4.5	0.5
4.63	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.8	0.5	5	0.5	4.44	0.5	3.89	0.9	4.7	0.5	4.7	0.7	5	0	5	0
2.5	0.5	4	0.5	3	0.5	2.8	0	3.44	0.3	4.22	0.2	2.9	0.2	4.4	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.6	0.5
4.88	0.7	3.75	0.4	4.4	0.5	5	0.3	4.67	0.5	4.78	0.4	5	0	4.9	0.3	4.12	0.2	4.6	0.5

Table No.3 depicts that SKG Sangha is successful in their sales related distribution policy and efforts as there is no noticeable difference between importance and satisfaction level of the farmers regarding distribution activities except the ‘focus of specific region’ where importance level is high and satisfaction level is less than neutral. However, Valse farmers’

opinion is differs from other villages as they show more importance to ‘installation and guidance by a qualified technician or installer’ but their satisfaction level is less than neutral. There is scope for improvement at Valase regarding this service. Organization has to pay attention on services given by technician and installer.

Table No. 4: Farmers’ Opinion on Promotion Policy

Sr.	Statement	Kasai Mala				Ambawade				Karanje				Kusavade				Limb			
		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc		Satisfactio		Importanc	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.																
1	Sales promotion incentives influence to purchase the biogas plant	4.83	0.4	4.92	0.3	5	0	4.4	0.5	4.33	0	5	0.6	5	0	4.75	0.5	4.7	0.7	4.9	0.3
2	The promotional information is clear	4.33	0.5	4.58	0.5	4.6	0.8	4.4	0.3	5	0.2	4.67	0	4.5	0	4.75	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.6	0.3
3	Early awareness through promotion	4.75	0.6	4.67	0.5	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.6	5	0	4.67	0.6	4.5	0.6	4.5	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.9	0.5
4	Ease to make the decision	4.17	0.7	3.83	0.8	4	0.5	4.8	0.5	4	0	4.67	0.6	3.75	0.6	4	0.6	3.9	0.4	4.3	0.3
5	Availability of Group Incentive	4.83	0.4	4.83	0.4	4.6	0.7	4.6	0.5	4.67	0	4.67	0.6	4.5	1	4.75	0.5	4.8	0.6	4.9	0.7
6	Company’s promotional Activities are relevant and attractive	4.75	0.4	4.5	0.5	4	0.9	4	0.6	4.67	0.6	4.67	0.6	4.25	0.6	4.75	0.5	4.5	0.6	4.6	0.3
7	Awareness campaign educate the community	4.58	0.5	4.83	0.4	5	0	4.8	0.2	4.67	0.6	5	0.6	4.75	1	4.75	0.5	4.7	0.5	4.7	0.5
8	Availability of social media platform	4.75	0.4	4.75	0.4	5	0	4.8	0.5	5	0.6	4	0	4.75	0.5	4.75	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.6	0.5
9	Positive impact of educational material	4.83	0.4	4.83	0.4	4.4	0	5	0.5	4.67	0	5	0.5	5	0.5	5	0	4.8	0.5	4.8	0.5
10	Motivation through success stores	4.17	0.7	4.58	0.6	4.8	0.6	4.6	0	4.33	0.6	4.67	0	4.5	0	4.25	0.5	4.7	0.4	4.6	0.4
11	Review from testimonials	3.92	1	4.52	0.6	2.6	0.5	4.2	0.5	4.67	0.2	3.67	0.6	3.5	0.6	4.5	0.5	4	0.5	4	0.5
12	Highly influenced by local leaders	4.42	0.6	4.75	0.6	4.6	0.9	4.2	0.3	5	0.6	5	0.5	4.75	0.3	4.25	0.6	4.6	0.8	4.5	0.5
13	Highly influenced by environmental	4.92	0.3	5	0	4.8	0.6	4.6	0.5	5	0	5	0	4.75	0.5	4.75	1	4.9	1	4.8	0.5

Mhasave		Shelkewadi				Shendre				Varye				Valse			
Satisfactio	Importanc																
Mean	S.D.																
4.75	0.4	4.38	0.2	5	0.4	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	4.9	0.3		
4.63	0.5	4.88	0.6	4.8	0	4.8	0	4.89	0.3	4.89	0.3	4.8	0.4	4.8	0.4		
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.4	4.8	0.5	4.6	0.5	4.78	0.4	4.78	0.7	4.7	0.5	4.8	0.6		
4	0.4	4	0.4	3.8	0.5	4.4	0.6	4.11	0.3	4.33	0.7	3.6	0.5	3.6	1		
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.6	4.8	0.8	5	0.6	5	0	4.89	0.3	4.8	0.4	4.9	0.3		
4.38	0.4	4.88	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.8	0	4.78	0.4	5	0	4.7	0.5	4.9	0.3		
4.63	0.5	4.75	0.4	4.6	0.6	4.6	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.67	0.5	4.9	0.3	4.7	0.5		
4.38	0.7	4.63	0.5	4.6	0.6	4.4	0.6	4.56	0.1	5	0	4.5	0.5	4.5	0.5		
4.75	0.5	4.88	0.5	4.8	0.6	4.8	0.6	5	0	5	0	5	0	4.9	0.3		
4.75	0.5	4.63	0.4	4.6	0.5	4.8	0.5	4.22	0.1	4.44	0.7	4.9	0.3	4.9	0.3		
4.38	0.5	4.25	0.5	4.4	0.6	3.2	0.5	3.78	0.9	4	0.1	3.9	0.7	3.2	0.3		
4.88	0.5	4.88	0.7	5	0.6	5	0.3	4.33	0.9	4.89	0.3	5	0	5	0		
4.13	0.4	4.5	0.4	4.8	0	4.8	0	5	0	4.89	0.3	5	0	5	0		

Table No. 4 shows that promotional efforts and policy of SKG sangha is quite satisfactory in all 10 villages. Farmers in Kasai Mala, Ambawade and Valse showed their dissatisfaction towards the ‘Review

from the testimonials. Here is the scope for improvement. SKG sangha has to pay the attention on this villages regarding this effort and have to find out the reason.

Major Findings:

SKG sangha is successful in delivering bio gas plant in most of the villages as per their designed policy. However farmers in Kasai Mala, Limb are slight dissatisfied about the 'availability of tailored bio gas system'. Ambawade, Varye and Valse farmers' showed high satisfaction towards 'less maintenance of the product'. Kusawade farmers' importance level is high regarding the biogas plant's innovative and efficient technology but satisfaction level is neutral.

SKG sangha is quiet successful in pricing policy as there is no noticeable difference between opinion of farmers in 10 villages and no gap in importance level and satisfaction level.

SKG Sangha is successful in their sales related distribution policy and efforts as there is no noticeable difference of opinion except the 'focus of specific region' where importance level is high and satisfaction level is less than neutral. However, Valse farmers' opinion is differs from other villages as they show more importance to 'installation and guidance by a qualified technician or installer' but their satisfaction level is less than neutral. Organization has to look in services given by technician and installer.

SKG sangha is quite satisfactory in all 10 villages to execute promotional sales related policy. Farmers in Kasai Mala, Ambawade and Valse showed their dissatisfaction towards the 'Review from the testimonials. Here is the scope for improvement. SKG sangha has to pay the attention on this villages regarding this effort and have to find out the reason.

Suggestion:

1. SKG Sangh should Target Older and Younger Farmers: Expand marketing efforts to farmers outside the 30-40 age group to capture a wider audience.

2. Explore Lower-Income Segments: Develop affordable biogas solutions for farmers earning less than 3 lakh annually.
3. Introduce Tailored Biogas Systems and Low-Maintenance Design: Provide customizable systems to meet diverse needs
4. Leverage Testimonials: Actively collect and use testimonials in marketing materials to build trust. Strengthen Local Networks: Build partnerships with local organizations to enhance distribution.
5. Also pay the attention on guidance and installation services and the people involved in those services.

Conclusion:

SKG Sangha's sales related product policies, pricing policies, distribution policy and promotional policy is successfully implemented by the organization in given 10 villages viz. Kasai Mala, Ambavade, Karanje, Kusawade, Limb, Mhasave, Shelkewadi, Shendre, Varye and Valase. After analyzing critically existing those policies it could conclude that SKG Sangha's Product policies, Pricing policies and promotion policy is quiet appreciable as there is no difference of opinion between importance level and satisfaction level of farmers towards those activities. However, there is a scope for improvement in distribution policy as it finds some differences in the farmers' opinion towards 'focus of specific region' where importance level is high and satisfaction level is less. However, Valse farmers' opinion is differs from other villages as they show more importance to 'installation and guidance by a qualified technician or installer' but their satisfaction level is less. Organization has to look in services given by technician and installer. There is scope for further research to determine the factors influence on

distribution effectiveness and promotional effectiveness in bio gas plant.

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